

Original Research Article

Intergenerational Educational Mobility across Caste Groups in Himachal Pradesh

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Abstract

The article examined intergenerational educational mobility in Himachal Pradesh among caste groups by using the Indian Human Development Survey 2011-12 dataset. The mobility matrix has been analyzed to calculate intergenerational educational mobility. The article reveals a huge disparity in intergenerational educational mobility among the different caste groups, where the general caste shows overall upward mobility in all educational levels compared to other castes. However, Sc and St categories show the improvement in their educational attainments.

Keywords: Intergenerational, Educational, mobility, Caste group

1. Introduction

India is a suitable case study example for intergenerational mobility for two reasons. First, Indian society was historically divided into different caste groups, which ultimately led to the exclusion of some social groups from social & economic domains. In ancient India, the individual's education, skills, occupation, and social status were determined by the particular caste of the individual to which they belonged. There was very little chance of an individual moving from a lower economic status to a higher one (M. S. Deshpande, 2010). Second, in a few decades, the Indian economy has shown rapid economic growth (Mehtabul Azam, 2015). With the rapid economic growth, inequality is one of the major challenges in achieving inclusive growth. Social mobility is one of the instrumental keys to exploring the factors that contribute to inequality and also focuses on bringing long-term equality to the nation (Singh et al., 2021). Recent studies (Duong, 2024; Lahiri & Nandi, 2020) reveal that disparities in intergenerational mobility among the different caste group households constitute one of the

fundamental dimensions of racial inequality in India, a debatable issue for researchers and policymakers. However, studies also prove that socially and economically deprived caste groups experience high poverty, low living standards, and less access to basic services such as education and health (Dutta, 2007), (P. Kumar & Singh, 2024). These obstacles are the main hurdle in the intergenerational educational and occupational mobility for deprived castes. However, (Ghosh, 2024) finds that caste practices affect physical mobility, access to credit, infrastructure, and ability to engage in a specific occupation and restrict lower caste access to local resources & income-earning opportunities which forces socially disadvantaged caste groups to sell their labour in low wages and in hazards conditions. Due to these strong intergenerational linkages, the labor market may not provide equal benefits to all its participants across all caste groups (Lahiri & Nandi, 2020). Education and occupation are the two major determinants of social mobility, which indicates a particular person's upward and downward mobility concerning their previous generation (Ekta et al., 2023). Thus, analysis of intergenerational educational mobility across the caste groups helps to identify the dimensions to which economic growth & modernization have broken traditional hierarchies and caste as well as class barriers to educational choice.

2. Literature Review

Examining intergenerational educational and occupational mobility is necessary because India has diverse socioeconomic conditions. (Ray & Majumder, 2010) identified low levels of educational and occupational mobility among the SC & ST caste groups by using NSSO data. However, occupational mobility is lower compared to education mobility, which indicates that only education progress is unable to transform occupational mobility. The father's earning & occupation affects the son's education and occupation directly and indirectly where lower/unskilled father-sons enter the same occupation in which his father is employed as compared to a higher educated and higher earnings father. The cost of education and training is the main reason behind it. Apart from this, there is an inter-caste disparity in occupation mobility which shows that socially deprived castes such as ST and SC show lower and persistent mobility than other caste groups (Reddy, 2015). A similar analysis was done by (Azam, 2013) estimated intergenerational occupational mobility in India by using the IHDS data. The study uses the 1945-54 to 1975-84 cohort to measure mobility. Occupation mobility was higher in 1975-84 compared to 1945-54 for all social category groups. However, in the 1965-84 birth cohort, SC & ST shows upward mobility as compared to other castes. (Ahmed & Nauriyal, 2021) finds the father's occupation is the main determinant of the son's educational achievements. As compared to less educated son of the father, the higher educated son of the father exhibits upward mobility in education and occupation. (Mondal, 2022a) examined how intergenerational educational & occupational mobility patterns vary among the different castes. It reveals that educational and occupational mobility varies with the social status of the household caste group. However, forward-caste children have upward mobility in terms of education and occupation compared to the other categories. Upper caste household shifted their occupation from agriculture and manual to professional occupations which is a sign of upward mobility and downward mobility highest among the SC and OBC caste groups. Along the same line, by using NSSO data find a moderate positive level of association between the father's occupation & son's educational attainments. The higher the income-earning occupation of the father, the higher the educational attainment of the son, and the lower the income-earning father occupation of the son lower the education attainment of the son. However, (M. Shahe Emran, 2024) finds a gender gap in educational mobility. It observed that absolute and relative mobility decreases with the father's educational attainments. However, there is a significant gender gap in rural and urban areas. The gender gap was lower in urban areas and higher in rural areas.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Intergenerational educational and occupational mobility has been one of the focus research areas of social scientists for the last two decades (Torche, 2015) (Siddiqui, 2023). A significant amount of the research has been done in developed countries. Indian researchers have also focused on this topic in the last few years (Asher et al., 2018), (R. Deshpande & Palshikar, 2008), (Iversen et al., 2017), (Lahiri & Nandi, 2020), (Lodh et al., 2021) (Mondal, 2022b), (Mehtabul Azam, 2015). These studies are related to major states of India. There are few specific studies related to the mountain state of India, particularly Himachal Pradesh. A study done by (A. Kumar, 2004) was limited only to the Kullu tehsil and only based on 150 sample sizes of the Lahuli migrants who migrated from

Lahual to Kullu district of Himachal Pradesh. Himachal Pradesh is one of the most progressive states in India. The census 2011 reported that 89.96% of the state population lives in rural areas. It also shows that 974 females per thousand males in Himachal Pradesh against the national average of 940. The state is a frontline performer in some of the human development indicators such as education, health, gender parity, and inter-group disparity. It has also a very low poverty level (Jodhka, 2015). It has ranked third in the National Family Health Survey-5, 2019-21. Despite this, Himachal Pradesh is a top performer state in India in terms of sustainable development goals. According to the Himachal Pradesh Human Development Report 2011-12, the state has relatively low poverty rates, high school attendance, and a rapid demographic transition, as well as a higher percentage of public expenditure. Against this background paper attempts to examine the intergenerational education mobility across the different caste groups.

3. Materials and Methods

IHDS 2011-12 data has been utilized in the present research. The survey was jointly organized by the National Council of Applied Research (NCAER). It covers 42,152 households, 384 districts, 1,420 villages, and 1042 urban zones across the country. Survey collects information on different aspects including education, health, economic status, occupations, fertility, social capital, gender, marriage, and geographic location of the households. In addition, IHDS data provides information on the household head's occupation, whether or not the husband/father resides in the same home (Azam, 2015; Mondal, 2022a). Apart from this, the survey provides a father's ID to determine the education and occupation of most male adults (20-65). Father-son pair matched by using the father and son ID whose age 20-65 years. However, data provides information on how many years a person's education is done rather than the level of education completed. This paper follows the educational category used by the (Mondal, 2022a). The overall years sent in school to gauge the educational attainments of fathers as well as sons. However, years of schooling are classified into five categories such as no schooling (0 years), primary education (1-5 years), secondary education (6-10 years), higher secondary (11-12), and bachelor and above (13-15 and more the 15 years).

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} P_{11} & P_{21} \\ P_{11} & P_{21} \end{bmatrix}$$

The study employed a mobility matrix introduced by (Xie & Killewald, 2013). A square matrix containing the marginal distribution of the son's occupation in comparison to those of his father. In an educational mobility matrix, the son's education is revealed in a row, and the father's education is shown in a matrix column. Besides this, the off-diagonal cell of the matrix exhibits upward and downward mobility, while the diagonal cell shows immobility. Nevertheless, none of the matrix cells have any representation of father education.

4. Results And Discussion

Table 1 provides the educational mobility matrix of fathers and sons. The matrix diagonal cell dominated the off-diagonal cell, which shows that the educated father-son attains a higher level of education compared to the uneducated & less educated fathers. The sons of fathers who have no education indicate only 10.71% attained the highest-level education graduation and above. The (table -1) reflects the highest upward mobility in sons of fathers who are educated up to graduation & above level, where 55.88% of sons attained the highest level of education. It shows that educated parents emphasize their children's education more because education leads to social status, improved employment, improved health conditions, higher salaries, career prospects, and job security (Chevalier et al., 2013).

Table 4.1: Overall Educational Mobility in Himachal Pradesh

Education of Father	Education of Son					Total
	No education	Up to Primary	Up to Secondary	Up to higher secondary	Graduate & above	
No education	3.57	10.71	34.82	40.18	10.71	100
Up to Primary	2.61	7.19	19.61	57.52	13.07	100
Up to Secondary	1.08	2.15	16.13	66.67	13.98	100
Up to higher secondary	0.00	3.15	7.09	55.12	34.65	100
Graduate & above	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.12	55.88	100
Total	1.73	5.59	17.92	53.95	20.88	100

(Source: IHDS 2011-12)

Education is not a homogeneous good because the quality of education offered in public & private sector schools is substantially different. Parents of wealthy/rich, highly educated, and higher socio-economic status households tend to enroll their children in private schools with better services, good infrastructure, and academic outcomes. On the other hand, uneducated, illiterate, undereducated, low-income households and low socio-economic status households enroll their children in government schools, which offer low or no fees. Due to this, there may be a disparity in intellectual levels, productivity, and skills among children (D. Kumar & Choudhury, 2021). This trend also varies with the social groups, where the General caste group shows overall upward mobility (table-2). In this category, sons of fathers with graduate or above persistently attained the same level of education. Even with the highest level of education, particularly graduates & above, the sons of a father with no education their sons also achieved higher secondary and graduate & above education. The OBC category also shows upward mobility like the General category, specifically secondary or higher secondary level, where the son of fathers with graduate and above education level indicates 100% same level of education attainment (table-3). SC and ST categories show some upward mobility, where the SC son's father with graduate and above education level educates 100% graduate and above level, although some of the no education sons of fathers shows remain in the same level. The ST category also shows upward mobility, where sons of fathers with graduate & above education reach 100% graduate. Apart from this, sons of fathers with no formal education also indicate some improvement: 42.86% attained higher secondary, and only 21.43 attained graduate and above education level (table 4 & 5).

Table 4. 2: Educational Mobility of General Category

Education of Father	Education of Son					Total
	No-education	Up to Primary	Up to Secondary	Up to higher secondary	Graduate and above	
No education	4.08	6.12	28.57	55.10	6.12	100
Up to Primary	1.47	4.41	19.12	57.35	17.65	100
Up to Secondary	0.00	1.85	20.37	68.52	9.26	100
Up to higher secondary	0.00	3.53	3.53	51.76	41.18	100
Graduate & above	0.00	0.00	0.00	46.88	53.13	100
Total	1.04	3.37	14.24	56.25	25.00	100

(Source: IHDS 2011-12)

Table 4.3: Educational mobility of OBC Category

Education of Father	Education of Son				Total
	Up to Primary	Up to Secondary	Up to higher secondary	Graduate & above	
No education	23.08	30.77	23.08	23.08	100
Up to Primary	0.00	50.00	50.00	0.00	100
Up to Secondary	0.00	22.22	55.56	22.22	100
Up to higher secondary	0.00	12.50	68.75	18.75	100
Graduate & above	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100
Total	6.12	26.53	48.98	18.37	100

(Source: IHDS 2011-12)

Table 4.4: Educational mobility of SC Category

Education of Father	Education of Son					Total
	No education	Up to Primary	Up to Secondary	Up to higher secondary	Graduate & above	
No education	2.78	11.11	52.78	25.00	8.33	100
Up to Primary	4.35	11.59	17.39	60.87	5.80	100
Up to Secondary	4.35	4.35	8.70	60.87	21.74	100
Up to higher secondary	0.00	4.35	17.39	56.52	21.74	100
Graduate & above	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	100
Total	3.29	9.21	24.34	51.32	11.84	100

(Source: IHDS 2011-12)

Table 4.5: Educational mobility of ST Category

Education of Father	Education of Son					Total
	No education	Up to Primary	Up to Secondary	Up to higher secondary	Graduate & above	
No education	7.14	14.29	14.29	42.86	21.43	100
Up to Primary	0.00	0.00	0.00	33.33	66.67	100
Up to Secondary	0.00	0.00	0.00	85.71	14.29	100
Up to higher secondary	0.00	0.00	0.00	66.67	33.33	100
Total	3.33	6.67	6.67	53.33	30.00	100

(Source: IHDS 2011-12)

Conclusion

The study found some upward mobility in all the categories, but compared to other caste groups, the General caste shows the highest overall mobility. There were some persistences found, especially at no educational level for all categories. Instead of persistence, the SC, ST, and OBC show some level of improvement in some of educational attainment. However, the study also finds that there were disparities in educational attainment across caste groups, which reflects that downward, upward, and persistent mobility in education in Himachal Pradesh has a caste connotation. It is evident from the findings that there are huge disparities in educational attainment across the different caste groups in Himachal Pradesh. To explore these disparities, there is a need for a micro-level study based on some excluded and low socio-economic status communities. However, to explore the regional disparities among the different caste groups, there micro-level study is required.

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